

Potentiometric Studies of Some Bivalent Metal Chelates of Sodium-4-hydroxy 3-formylazobenzene 4'-sulphonate

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Complexation equilibria of metal complexes of $\text{UO}_2(\text{II})$, $\text{Pb}(\text{II})$, $\text{Hg}(\text{II})$ and $\text{Mg}(\text{II})$ with sodium-4-hydroxy 3-formylazobenzene 4'-sulphonate (SHFBS) have been carried out potentiometrically. The stability constants of these chelates were determined in 42% (v/v) ethanol-water medium by Calvin-Bjerrum titration technique at 25° in a medium of 0.2M ionic strength. The logarithm of the stepwise stability constants 4.83 and 4.19 for $\text{UO}_2(\text{II})$; 4.08 and 3.51 for $\text{Pb}(\text{II})$; 3.73 and 3.22 for $\text{Hg}(\text{II})$ and 3.19 and 2.96 for $\text{Mg}(\text{II})$ were obtained for SHFBS chelates. Free energy changes (ΔF) of the chelation reaction have been evaluated. A probable structure of the metal chelate formed in solution is also suggested.

Salicylaldehyde complexes of several bivalent metal ions have been studied by Mellor *et al.*¹. The effects of substitution of various groups with respect to stability in α -hydroxy aldehydes have been studied by Calvin and Wilson². Various metal chelates of 2,4-dihydroxy and 2,5-dihydroxy benzaldehydes have been studied by Menon *et al.*³ Recently Trivedi *et al.*⁴ reported the synthesis and the chelating tendencies of SHFBS with some bivalent metal ions. In the present paper, the chelating tendencies of SHFBS with $\text{UO}_2(\text{II})$, $\text{Pb}(\text{II})$, $\text{Hg}(\text{II})$ and $\text{Mg}(\text{II})$ chelates have been determined and reported along with their free energy changes (ΔF) of the reaction.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials: Sulphanilic acid, salicylaldehyde, perchloric acid, sodium perchlorate etc. were of AnalaR (B.D.H.) grade reagents. Sodium hydroxide (E. Merck) was dissolved in Pyrex beaker in distilled water free from CO_2 and was kept overnight over lime. The solution was standardised by titrating a diluted portion of it potentiometrically against a standard oxalic acid solution. A.R. metal nitrates or sulphates were used for preparing metal solutions.

Apparatus: A Cambridge (Bench type) pH-meter with glass and calomel electrodes was used. The measurements were checked before and after the titration with standard buffers⁷.

Synthesis and pK of the ligand: The synthesis and dissociation constant of the SHFBS have been discussed in our previous communication⁴. The pK of the SHFBS was calculated as 6.32 employing the Irving and Rossotti⁵ method.

pH-metric titrations : For metal-ligand systems the following mixtures were prepared and titrated separately with standard sodium hydroxide solution (0.2M) :

Mixture A : 1.0 ml. of $4 \times 10^{-2} M$ $HClO_4$ + 10 ml. of 1.0M $NaClO_4$.

Mixture B : Mixture A and 25 ml. of $5 \times 10^{-3} M$ ligand (SHFBS).

Mixture C : Mixture B and 5 ml. of $5 \times 10^{-3} M$ Metal ions [$UO_2(II)$, $Pb(II)$, $Hg(II)$ and $Mg(II)$ respectively].

The titrations were carried out in 42% (v/v) ethanol-water medium at 25°. Sodium perchlorate was added to maintain an ionic strength of 0.2M. The total volume in each case was 50 ml.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Formation curves for the metal-ligand system (Fig. 2) were drawn between \bar{n} and p^L . The values of these terms were obtained by the Bjerrum's⁶ method modified by Calvin and Wilson².

Curve L, Fig. 1, indicates two inflections corresponding to the neutralization of free acid and -OH group of the ligand. The ligand being a monoprotic (HL) neutralises one equivalent of base to yield one buffer region in its potentiometric equilibrium curve

FIG. 1

Fig. 1. Potentiometric titration of SHFBS in the absence of and in the presence of metal ions, pH vs. a where 'a' is the moles of sodium hydroxide added per mole of ligand. Curves L, A, B, C and D are ligand, $UO_2(II)$, $Pb(II)$, $Hg(II)$ and $Mg(II)$ respectively. Dotted lines show the formation of a precipitate. In each case total volume = 50 ml, $\mu = 0.2M$ ($NaClO_4$), Temp. = $25^\circ \pm 0.1^\circ$.

When 5 : 1 mixture of ligand to metal is titrated against standard alkali (curves A, B, C and D) the systems are lower than the corresponding pH value in system L (Fig. 1) indicating the liberation of proton due to the complex formation. The complex equilibria may be represented by the following equations :

The precipitation was observed beyond pH 6.35, 6.45, 7.0 and 7.7 in the cases of $UO_2(II)$, $Pb(II)$, $Hg(II)$ and $Mg(II)$ respectively. Despite the tendency of metal ions to hydrolyse, such effects have been ignored in this work, since the complexes are stable in the pH range studied.

The order of stability of bivalent metal complexes is found to be $UO_2 > Pb > Hg > Mg$ and are shown in Table 1. The values of overall changes in free energies ($\Delta F = -RT \ln K$) are also calculated at 25° .

FIG. 2

Fig. 2. Formation curves of metal-SHFBS systems

Curve A— $UO_2(II)$ —SHFBS system

Curve B— $Pb(II)$ —SHFBS system

Curve C— $Hg(II)$ —SHFBS system

Curve D— $Mg(II)$ —SHFBS system.

TABLE 1

The values of stability constants and free energies at 25°

Metal ion	$\log K_1$	$\log K_2$	$\log \beta_2$	ΔF (K.cal/mole)
UO ₂ (II)	4.83±0.02	4.19±0.02	9.02	-12.38
Pb(II)	4.08±0.02	3.51±0.02	7.59	-10.42
Hg(II)	3.73±0.02	3.22±0.02	6.95	- 9.54
Mg(II)	3.19±0.02	2.96±0.02	6.15	- 8.44

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